

The Good Eagle or The Bad Elephant: Correlating the Features and Life Cycle of an Umbrella and an Eagle (Symbols of NDC) with the NDC Government Projects and John Mahama's 24hr Economy Policy in Ghana

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12786599

Disclaimer: This article seeks not to portray all elephants as bad animals but when some wild Elephants go beyond limits, the problems must be identified and better alternatives must be considered.

Summary:

The National Democratic Congress (NDC) government and John Mahama's 24hr economy policy in Ghana can be creatively correlated with the features and life cycle of an umbrella and an eagle. This write-up explores the fascinating parallels between the two.

Features and Life Cycle of an Umbrella and an Eagle:

1. Social Intervention Programs (NDC): Portable and collapsible (umbrella) $\approx$ Migration and adaptability (eagle) while the _NPP's Elephant Feeds with even all the independent members of their family to their own benefit.

2. Infrastructure Development (NDC): Waterproof and protective (umbrella) $\approx$ Waterproof feathers and sharp talons (eagle) but the NPP's Elephant Trunk has loads of greed_* 📄 selling government properties to themselves.

3. Economic Stability (NDC): Sturdy frame and ribs (umbrella) ≈ Strong wings and bones (eagle) but the NPP's Elephant has a Destructive path destroying everything.
4. Good Governance (NDC): Handle and grip (umbrella) ≈ Talons and grasp (eagle) but the *_NPP's Elephant is Rampaging through (destroying) the rule of law_*
5. Gradual Economic Growth (NDC): Compact to full-size (umbrella) ≈ Nestling to soaring (eagle) but the __NPP's Elephant Forget the past_* 🙄 promises without nurturing anything.
6. 24hr Economy Policy (John Mahama): Windproofing and resilience (umbrella) ≈ Aerodynamic wings and resilience (eagle) but the __NPP's Elephant Feeds lying down unconcerned*
7. Streamlined Processes (NDC): Automatic open/close (umbrella) ≈ Instinctual hunting and nesting (eagle) but __NPP's Elephant standing up while feeding looks for next opportunity to exploit the people.
8. Transparency and Accountability (NDC): LED lights and visibility (umbrella) ≈ Exceptional vision and hunting prowess (eagle) but the NPP's Elephant Tusks (teeth) of corruption is overwhelming.

MORE DETAILS:

The National Democratic Congress (NDC) government and John Mahama's 24hr economy policy in Ghana can be creatively correlated with the features and life cycle of an umbrella and an eagle. This write-up explores the fascinating parallels between the two.

Features and Life Cycle of an Umbrella and an Eagle:

1. Portable and collapsible (umbrella) ≈ Migration and adaptability (eagle): Just as an umbrella is portable and adaptable, eagles migrate and adapt to different environments, demonstrating their remarkable flexibility. This correlation highlights the NDC's social intervention programs, such as LEAP, which are expanded to be flexible and accessible to those in need.
2. Waterproof and protective (umbrella) ≈ Waterproof feathers and sharp talons (eagle): The NDC's investments in infrastructure development, such as roads and bridges, are like a waterproof umbrella, providing protection and connectivity for citizens. Eagles' waterproof feathers and sharp talons enable them to thrive in various weather conditions, similar to how the NDC's infrastructure development protects citizens from economic challenges.

3. Sturdy frame and ribs (umbrella) ≈ Strong wings and bones (eagle): The NDC's efforts to stabilize the economy, such as implementing fiscal discipline and promoting private sector growth, are like the sturdy frame and ribs of an umbrella, providing a strong foundation for development. Eagles' strong wings and bones support their majestic flight, similar to how the NDC's economic stability enables Ghana's growth.

4. Handle and grip (umbrella) ≈ Talons and grasp (eagle): The NDC's commitment to good governance, transparency, and accountability is like the handle and grip of an umbrella, ensuring that power is held securely and used for the benefit of all. Eagles' talons and grasp enable them to hold onto prey and perches, similar to how the NDC's good governance ensures a firm grip on power.

5. Compact to full-size (umbrella) ≈ Nestling to soaring (eagle): The NDC's approach to economic growth, focusing on gradual and sustainable development, is like the compact to full-size range of an umbrella, allowing for flexibility and adaptability. Eagles grow from nestlings to soaring adults, expanding their wingspans up to 2.5 meters, similar to how the NDC's economic growth enables Ghana to soar.

6. Windproofing and resilience (umbrella) ≈ Aerodynamic wings and resilience (eagle): The NDC's 24hr economy policy, aimed at promoting economic activity beyond traditional hours, is like a windproof umbrella, designed to withstand challenges and thrive in diverse conditions. Eagles' aerodynamic wings and resilience enable them to fly up to 240 km/h, similar to how the NDC's policy promotes economic resilience.

7. Automatic open/close (umbrella) ≈ Instinctual hunting and nesting (eagle): The NDC's efforts to streamline processes and reduce bureaucracy are like the automatic open/close feature of an umbrella, making it easier to access services and support. Eagles' instinctual hunting and nesting abilities enable them to thrive in various environments, similar to how the NDC's streamlined processes enable Ghana to thrive.

8. LED lights and visibility (umbrella) ≈ Exceptional vision and hunting prowess (eagle): The NDC's commitment to transparency and accountability is like the LED lights on an umbrella, shining a light on progress and challenges, ensuring visibility and trust. Eagles' exceptional

vision and hunting prowess enable them to spot prey from up to 8 km away, similar to how the NDC's transparency enables citizens to see the government's progress.

THE GREEDY NPP ELEPHANT

1. *_Rampaging through the rule of law_* 🚔: A bad elephant tramples on the rules and regulations, just like the NPP government's corruption disregards the laws and constitution of Ghana, resulting in a high increase in corruption cases since they took office.

2. *_Forgetting the past_* 🙄: A bad elephant forgets the lessons of the past and repeats the same mistakes, just like the NPP government's corruption ignores the mistakes of previous governments and continues to perpetuate corruption, with many of Ghanaians saying the government has failed to address corruption especially with one district one factory policy.

3. *_Tusks of corruption_* 🐘: A bad elephant uses its tusks to manipulate and control others, just like the NPP government's corruption uses its power and influence to exploit and oppress others, resulting in great increase in human rights abuses.

4. *_Trunk-loads of greed_* 🐘: Greedy Elephants can feed up to 18hours a day and take in 140litres (37 gallons of water) a day. A bad elephant consumes everything in sight, just like the NPP government's corruption is driven by greed and a desire for more power and wealth, with the government spending more on unnecessary projects than on essential services.

5. *_Feeding with all the family_* 👨👩👧👦: A bad elephant feeds with its all family members, just like the NPP government's corruption prioritizes the interests of family members and cronies, with most of government contracts going to party loyalists.

6. *_Feeding lying down_* 🐘: A bad elephant eats while lying down, just like the NPP government's corruption is comfortable with corrupt practices and sees no need to change, with only few of corruption cases prosecuted. *_Bad elephant eating lying down_* 🤢: A bad elephant eats lying down, just like the NPP government's corruption is shameless and brazen in its corrupt practices, with many Ghanaians saying corruption is getting worse.

7. *_Feeding standing up_* 🐘: A bad elephant eats while standing up, just like the NPP government's corruption is always on the lookout for the next opportunity to exploit and corrupt, with a high increase in corruption cases involving government officials.

9. *_Destructive path_* 🐘 : A bad elephant leaves a trail of destruction in its wake, just like the NPP government's corruption has left Ghana's economy and institutions in shambles.

Conclusion:

This creative correlation and metaphor highlights the fascinating parallels between the features and life cycle of an umbrella and an eagle with the NDC government projects and John Mahama's 24hr economy policy in Ghana. The comparison showcases the adaptability, resilience, and growth-oriented approach of the NDC government and John Mahama's policy.

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